

Human Right and Equality for Women

Dr. (Smt.) Neeraj

Assistant Professor, Department of Political Science, Govt. Girls Degree College, Kurawali, Mainpuri, Uttar Pradesh, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. (Smt.) Neeraj

Abstract

Every woman should lead a life of respect, equality and decency, free from only form of fear, force, violence and discrimination. According to Article 21 of the Constitution every citizen, including women is entitled to the right to life and dignity. Section 354A of the Indian Penal Code Criminalizes harassment.

Among the International human rights treaties, this convention takes an important place in bringing the female half of humanity into the focus of human rights concerns. The spirit of the convention is rooted in the goals of the United Nations is to reaffirm faith in fundamental human rights in the dignity and worth of the human person and in the equal rights of men and woman.

In Indian society where about half of the total population and three fifths of the females are illiterate (2011 Census), Customs and tradition bond beliefs and practices cannot be dispelled overnight. It is also easy to create a strong public opinion against these practices, Legislations, of course make some impact but it can only be introduced very cautiously and in stages.

Women search for equality has definitely come to its saturation point but yet full satisfaction is not achieved by women. Women rights are achievements of women inquest for equality but there are miles to go for equality and empowerment.

The Convention on the Elimination of all forms of Discrimination against women establishes a framework and a procedure for governments and civil Societies to work together in ensuring that women's basic rights are fully realized. The universal ratification and enforcement of CEDAW would increase countries abilities to advance women's human rights, resulting in a healthier, more just, wealthy and safe world for everyone.

Keywords: Human rights, Women rights, Equality, Justice, Discrimination

Introduction

We are all entitled to Human rights. These Include the right to live free from violence and discrimination to enjoy the highest attainable standard of Physical and mental health to be educated to own property to vote and to earn an equal wage but across the globe many women and girls still face discrimination on the basis of sex and gender. Gender, inequality underpins many problems which disproportionately affect women and girls, such as domestic and sexual violence, lower pay, lack of access to education and inadequate health care.

A patriarchal and oppressed Indian society with inhumane caste systems supposedly based on religious faith, however, their religious beliefs are obviously not understood since their masculine domination acts against the religious base of men and women living as equals. Despite modernization, women's status remained low and devalued well into the 20th century. Women in India are beginning to follow the direction that the women of the Western world took more

than eighty years ago; demanding treatment as human equals. However, it has become more and more evident as the revolution ages that Indian women may have to adapt the Western feminist method to their very traditional and religious culture. India has different complications that put the development of women in a completely altered context than their Western counterparts. Although the key targets remain similar: improvement of health care, education and job opportunities in order to gain equality between men and women in the various settings of public society, the workplace, the school yard and possibly the most fundamental setting of all the home. Women are striving to be independent on the equal level of men. The additional complexities that the women of India must also challenge are the caste system, the heavy religious customs, older and more traditional roles of the sexes, as well as the even stronger power that men hold in India. The status was at one time accepted, but with the Western women's revolution and perception, the role is slowly succeeding in its development

through both independent groups of women and national and worldwide organizations based on the goal of gaining equality. They have all accomplished much, but have yet to overthrow the male dominated society in India. Demands for human equality basically demands for women's human rights.

The term women's human right and the set of practices that accompany its use, is continuously evolving International attention and attraction to improve the status of women. The women's movements in 1980 and 1990 pulled greater attention worldwide to study the problems and atrocities faced by women every day. In the evolution of what is becoming a global women's movement, the women's Human Right served as a customer accepted practice, which is for the development of political strategies and concentrate political practices. Hence the women's Human Right has become a vehicle for women to develop their political skills necessary for the twenty first century, but this status could not get in moment there is a long history of struggle behind it which is fought by the aware women to get their human rights equal to men.

Women's rights are the fundamental human rights that were enshrined by the United Nations for every human being on the planet nearly 70 years ago. These rights include the right to live free from violence, slavery and discrimination, to be educated to own property, to vote, and to earn a fair and equal wage. Winning rights for women is about more than giving opportunities to any individual woman or girl, it is also about changing how countries and communities work. It involves changing laws and policies, winning hearts and minds and investing in strong women's organizing and movements.

Woman search for equality in disguise of women rights

The adoption of a Universal Declaration of Human Rights 70 years ago has made the countries of the world recognize human rights to be universal and fundamental. The United Nations Charter was the first Global treaty which called for equaling between women and men. The UN Charter, in its preamble, declared their faith "in the fundamental human rights, in the dignity and worth of human person in the equal rights of men and women and of nations large and small." The UN Charter goes on to proclaim that one of the purpose is to achieve International cooperation in promoting and encouraging result for human rights and fundamental freedom for all people without distinction as to race, sex, and language of religion. The UN Charter recognizes that everyone has the right to take part in the Government of his country directly or indirectly through freely chosen representative. It has equalized the status of men and women in the enjoyment and exercise of political rights in accordance with the provision of the United Nations and of the universal declaration of human rights. The document clearly states what should be obvious but too often is no. All human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights. They are endowed with reason and conscience. In this entire world where do women rights begin? The women conditions are screwing and depicting a miserable picture of the violation of their human rights. Human rights and particularly women's rights must also be defined as being seen and treated in domestic and private areas. The participation of women in the political and the social realm

allows for delegitimizing discrimination against women and achieving genuine equality not only under the law. It also affects individual cultures that previously denied woman the possibility of an education and confined them to a world of silence.

Women's Rights and International Forum

It was UN commitment to women's rights include the establishment of a commission on the status of women in 1949, the UN sponsorship of the decade for women and for UN meetings on women, beginning in 1975, in Mexico city and ending in 1995 in Beijing, which were followed by the Beijing plus 5 meetings in June of 2000. The establishment of CEDAW 1979 and the 1993 world conference on Human Rights in Vienna were important in codifying and re-emphasizing the centrality of women's human rights. As an instrument invoked by women's groups and interpreted by its monitoring.

Concern for the women's fundamental freedom has not only been expressly dealt in the universal declaration of Human Rights or the two International covenants on Human Rights. The International Labour Organization (ILO) has been focusing on women and gender equality in the world of work since its creation in 1919. It adopted (i) convention on equal remuneration for men and women workers for work of equal value, 1951 (ii) convention concerning night work of women employed in industry, 1948 and (iii) convention concerning maternity protection (revised) 1952. Many conventions specially concerning women has been adopted by the UN General Assembly, these are (i) convention on the political rights of women, 1952; (ii) convention on the nationality of married women, 1957; (iii) convention against discrimination in education, 1960, prohibiting discrimination on account of sex (iv) convention on the elimination of all forms of discrimination against women, 1979 and (v) convention on the rights of the child, 1989 with special emphasis on girl child.

Convention on the elimination of all forms of discrimination against women (1979):

Among the International human rights treaties, this convention takes an important place in bringing the female half of humanity into the focus of human rights concerns. The spirit of the convention is rooted in the goals of the United Nations is to reaffirm faith in fundamental human rights in the dignity and worth of the human person and in the equal rights of men and human.

In its preamble, the convention explicitly acknowledges that "extrusive discrimination against women continues to exist", and emphasis that such discrimination "violates the principles of equality of rights and respect for human dignity." The convention spells out the meaning of equality and how it can be achieved. In so doing, the convention establishes not only an international bill of rights for women, but also an agenda for action by countries to guarantee the enjoyment of those rights. It commits states to endeavoring to eliminate sex-role stereotype (Article 5); to eliminate traffic in women and the exploitation of the prostitution of women (Article 6); to providing rights surrounding maternity such as protection from dismissal on the grounds of pregnancy, the right to maternity leave, and the right to special protection for women in types of work

proved harmful to them (Article 11). It may be said that the convention intends to end discrimination and not to enumerate a list of rights for women.

International Decade for Women: Under the auspices of the UN, the world conference of the International women's year was held in 1975 in Mexico City and it was decided to observe the decade of 1976-85 as United Nations decade for women. The conference adopted the declaration of Mexico on equality of women and their contribution to development and peace. The need to define, understand and implement women's rights gained global recognition during the International decade for women 1976-85. In 1980, the world conference of the United Nations decade for women was held in Copenhagen.

Governments must create or strengthen independent national institutions for the protection and promotion of these rights, including the human rights of women, as recommended by the world conference. In Human Rights, develop a comprehensive human rights education programme to raise awareness among women of their human rights and also raise awareness among others of the human rights of woman and ensure the implementation of the recommendations of the world conference on Human Rights for the full integration and mainstream of the human rights of women. Government must strengthen cooperation and coordination between the commission on the status of women, the commission on Human Rights, the commission for social development, the commission on sustainable development, the commission on crime prevention and criminal justice, the United Nations Human Rights treaty mentioning bodies, including the committee on the elimination of discrimination against women, and the United Nations, Development Fund for Women, the International Research and Training Institute for the advancement of women, the United Nations Development Programme the United Nations children's fund and other organizations of the united nations system, acting within their mandates, in the promotion of the human rights of women and improve cooperation between the division for the advancement of women and the centre for Human Rights.

Women's Rights in India: In Indian society where about half of the total population and three fifths of the females are illiterate (1991 census) customs and tradition bound beliefs and practices cannot be dispelled overnight. It is also easy to create a strong public opinion against these practices. Legislations, of course make some impact but it can only be introduced very cautiously and in stages.

The important rights assured by the constitution of India to women like women.

1. Right to equality, that is equally before law, equal protection of the live not discriminating against any person an grounds of sex and is matter of public employment on the gender grounds.
2. Right to freedom, that is freedom of speech, expression, residence, occupation and mobility.
3. Right against exploitation that is against forced labour (beggar).
4. Right to freedom of religion, that is, professing practices and propagating religion freely.

5. Right to property, that is acquiring, holding and selling property.
6. Cultural, educational rights, concerning one's culture and seeking admission to educational institutions.
7. Right to constitutional remedies, that is approaching courts for enforcing fundamental rights.

Besides assuring these fundamental rights the state has also been empowered to enact special laws for protecting the interests of and giving preferential treatment to females and weaker section. On this ground the state has been taking legislative measures formative to time for performing its obligations of bringing in a social order in which justice prevails.

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